

UNDERSTANDING OF GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES: A STUDY ON FACULTY MEMBERS OF COLLEGE IN ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract

For the last few decades green human resources has been the buzzword in the organizational context. The objective of this paper is to what extent the faculty members working in college at Andhra Pradesh. Understand the green human resource management practices. Hence, this study adopts the descriptive research design. Green human resource planning, green recruitment, green selection, green job description and green induction are the variables taken as independent, variables. Environment performance has been considered as the dependent variables. For these variables questionnaire has been constructed to collect the primary data among the faculty members working in colleges at Srikakulam District Andhra Pradesh. A sample of 120 faculty members approached through convenience sampling method. The collected data are entered into SPSS package. Further, descriptive statistics and correlation analysis is applied. The study result revealed that the faculty members are well aware of green human resource practices. The study also found that the adoption of green practices has the positive relationship with increased environmental performance and helps promote institution image.

Keywords: Green Resource Planning, Green Recruitment, Green Selection, Green Job Description, Green Induction and Environmental Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Now-a-days green human resource management has become a key business strategy for the eco-friendly environment in the organizations. Human resource department has playing an effective role for making the office as green. This research focuses on various green human resource practices implemented by the colleges in Andhra Pradesh.

Green movement and green human resource are still in the initial stage due to infancy. People awareness about the green within organization has significantly contributing the green environment. Waste management, recycling, reducing the carbon footprint, using and producing green products are the best green practices (Opatha, 2013). Majority of the employees strongly agreed about the environment and they exhibit greater commitment and job satisfaction towards environment. It shows that everyone is ready to go green. Green human resource management practices are multifaceted and require constant monitoring to recognize its potential impact on human resource management issues. The green human resource management involves specific policies and practices. Environment, social and economic balance are the basic pillars for sustainability of the organization (Wehrmeyer, 1996).

Now-a-days, corporate world is changing from a business oriented perspective to competency based green economy. The world is moving towards green economy, hence the corporate has responsibility to go green (Parul Deshwal, 2015). The term green human resource refers to promoting the sustainable employee practices with the help of interface of every employee. The aim of the green is to increase the awareness among the employees on the issue of sustainability. Green human resource deals with the human resource activities, which are environment friendly and promote the sustainable use of resources in the organizations (Beard and Dees, 2000). Business organizations to trim down employee for carbon footsteps through teleconferencing, sharing the car, telecommunication, filing electronically, virtual interviews, recycling, online training, etc. This study is focus on green human resource management as a strategic initiative by the colleges to promote sustainable environmental performance.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Vuyokazai Mtembu (2022) determined the relationship between knowledge of green human resource management practices and its implementation within the organization. Questionnaires used to collect the data from employees. Thematic analysis used to analyze data. Half of human resource practitioners stated that they are aware about the concept green human resource management. But, they are reflected moderate knowledge and understanding of green human resource management principles in the institutions. There was no policy framework in the form of green human resource management activities and its implementation within the organization. There was a strong correlation between green human resource management policies and implementation of green human resource management activities.

Volkan Ugur (2021) analysed the relationship between demographic profile of the employees and environmental sensitivity. Environmental sensitivity scale was used to assess participants' environmental sensitivity level with 3 dimensions namely air-water-soil pollution, ecological balance practices, participation to environmental sensitivity. Education, age, gender and marital status are demographic variable used for analysis of participants. There is significant difference among the age groups with environment sensitivity. It is also found that marital status has the relationship with on environmental practices. There was significant difference between male and female according to their environmental sensitivity and awareness.

Sathya and Jothi Jayakrishnan (2019) observed the challenges of green practices and its effect on environmental performance. In current new globalization era, the awareness on the environmental issues such as pollution, emission and waste become crucial part to society and community. Meanwhile, organization had faced pressure from shareholders and other stakeholders to promote the sustainability of environmental performance in organization. So, organization needs to take the initiative to increase the awareness and contribution of employees towards environmental sustainability.

Richa Chaudhary (2018) stated that green human resource management practices affect potential employees' intent to pursue career in an organization. Employees' personal environmental orientation and firm environment performance are analyzed in this research. It is found that green human resource management on job pursuit intention through

organizational attractiveness was moderated by environmental orientation of prospective applicants.

Monicah Wanjiku kuna (2017) revealed that green recruitment and selection, green human resource performance management, green training and development, green pay and reward have positive and significant relationship with organizational effectiveness of Universities in Kenya. It is concluded that during recruitment and selection, the management seeks to recruit staff and personnel that are conversant and ready to apply their skills and expertise to better the ecological surrounding. Employees recruited are not only left on their own to work out the plan, but are also coached and trained on their specific matters and issues that relate to the environment. Motivation of the staff had a higher relationship compared to the other variables. However, the reward system was not adequate and satisfactory, which was evident by delayed rewards or compensations towards the met green standards to the employees and unclear promotional framework.

3. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Employees' behaviour and attitude should be transform and create good intension towards green practices. Employees green procedure promotes the green human resource practices across the world. Green employees involved in hiring of individual with organizational sustainability and high technical and management skill with good knowledge of environmental issues. These employees create awareness among the employees. Transform the normal employees into the green employees by providing them training. It helps to promote the morale and the attitude of the employees towards the benefit of the individual, society, organization and environment sustainability (Sharma and Gupta, 2009). In green employees, job analysis procedure generally focus on environmental aspect such as environmental reporting duties and responsibilities identification and influencing of candidates with environment management related experience. Environment centered testing and interviewing technique enables the managers to identify candidates, who are fit for the environment centered jobs (Renwick, et. al., 2008). It is ensured that the selected employees should posses' personality and attitudes towards the reducing waste, show creativity and innovative idea for the environment sustainability. Sharma and Gupta (2009) stated that environment management is the key element for green human resource management. Hence, training and development should focus on development of employees' skill, knowledge, attitudes and behavior about environment conservation and environment initiatives. The activities should include training the employees working method in order to conserve energy, reduce waste, create environmental awareness and provide opportunity to engage employees in solving environment problem. It also enhanced the ability of the employees to develop proactive attitudes towards organizational sustainability (Carter and Dresner, 2001).

4. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to analyse the faculty members' perception about the green human resource management practices in their institution at Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh. Further, it also examined the relationship between green human resource management practices and environmental performance of the institution.

6. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Green human resource planning, green recruitment, green selection, green job description and green induction have been related with environmental performance of the institutions.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is the way of systematically approaching the research problem. It is a careful investigation specially through search for new facts in any branch of knowledge.

Type of Research

This study applied descriptive research approach. The intent of this tradition of enquiry is to get a picture of a situation, behavior or attitudes before planning future research (Kane, et. al., 2001). This study analyses the faculty members' perception towards the implementation of green human resource practices in colleges situated in Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh.

Sample Size

This study population entails faculty members working colleges in Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh. Hence, the top 10 colleges as per NIRF ranking have been considered. In these 10 colleges, around 620 faculty members are working. So the population is 620 faculty members. Out of 620, 150 faculties members has been approached through phone call than their mail id has been collected. The sample respondents have been selected through convenience sampling method. Further, the questionnaire has been sent to their mail id. Out of 150 distributed questionnaire 120 faculty members properly filled and return to the researcher. Hence, the sample size of the study is 120.

Questionnaire Design

In this study, GHRM practices have five dimensions namely green human resource planning, green recruitment, green selection, green job description and green induction. These tools are taken from various authors. GHRM practices has been taken is independent variables. Environmental performance has been taken as dependent variables, constructs and measures has been presented to Table – 1.

Table 1: Constructs and Measures

Construct	Statement	Source
Green Human Resource Planning	Planned of number of employees capable of carrying out environmental activities.	Arulraja, Opatha and Nawarathna, 2015.
	Green management initiates have enough skills.	
	Applied strategy the preserve the environment.	
	Appointed the consultants to forecast the environmental works.	
Green Recruitment	Communicating the environmental performance through recruitment message.	Jakson, et. al., 2011, Renwick, et. al., 2013, Opatha, 2013.
	Priority to the candidates with green mind set.	
	Using e-technology in the recruitment process.	
	Using green employees branding to attract the employees.	
Green Selection	Includes an environmental work force through green recruitment by raising awareness.	Renwick, et. al., 2012, Opatha, 2013, Revill, 2000.
	Candidates selection based on awareness of greening in job.	
	Preferring candidates who are conscious about green policies in private life.	
	Selection team asked the question relating to green HRM.	
Green Job Description	Selecting criteria for selecting candidates with environmental awareness.	Renwick, et. al., 2013, Jabour, et. al., 2010.
	Environmental dimension is included in the job description.	
	Green competency is required as a special component in job specification.	
	Environmental management function has been developed within the organization.	
Green Induction	Encouraging team work to preserve the environment.	Revil, 2000, North, 1997.
	Conduct orientation programme to the employees for increase awareness of green culture.	
	Providing necessary information on green management for new employees.	
	Ensuring that new employees are aware of the importance of environment responsibilities.	
Environmental Performance	Making the employees to engage in green interpersonal citizenship behavior.	Chow and Chen, 2012.
	Disposal of waste without affecting environment.	
	Practise of recycling of materials in the organization.	
	Usage of renewable energy and sustainable fuels is increasing.	
	Frequency of environmental mishaps is reduced.	
	Conservation of water usage.	
	Energy usage is having conserved.	

Statistical Tool Applied

In order to answer the research objective frequency analysis, description statistics such as mean and standard deviation and correlation test have been applied.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to examine the faculty members perception towards green HRM practices in colleges. Frequently analysis, mean and standard deviation and correlation analysis have been applied. The result is interpreted as below.

Table 2: Profile of the Respondents

Gender	Male	77	74.6
	Female	43	25.4
Age	Less than 30	58	28.7
	31-40	28	51.6
	Above 40	34	19.7
Experience	Less than 5	72	60.0
	5 to 10	38	31.7
	Above 10	10	8.3
Designation	Assistant Professor	81	67.5
	Associate Professor	28	23.3
	Professor	11	9.2

Source: Primary Data Computed

Frequency analysis is applied to know the number of employees in the group. The result is displayed in the table-1. Out of 120 sample respondents, 77 (64.2%) belongs to male category and 43 (35.8%) belongs to female category. It shows that male employees have participated more in the survey. Age is classified into 3 groups namely less than 30 years old, 31 years to 40 years old and above 40 years old. 48.3 percent of the employees belong to less than 30 years old, 28.3 percent of the employees are in the age group of 30 to 40 years old and 19.7 percent of the employees are in the above 40 years old group. In the case of family type, 74.6 percent of the employees are living in nuclear family system and 25.4 percent of the employees are living in the joint family system. In case of experience, 60 percent of the employees are having less than 5 years experience, 31.7 percent of the employees are having 5 to 10 years experience, 8.3 percent of the employees are having above 10 years experience. For designation 67.5 percent are assistant professors, 23.3 percent are associate professors and 9.2 percent are professors. From the frequency analysis, it is observed that all the categories of employees are participated in the survey. Hence, the sample respondents are heterogeneous groups.

In this research, green human resource planning, green recruitment, green selection, green job description, green induction, green induction and environmental performance have been analysis from the faculty members point of view. To know the employees perception about the implementation of green human resource practices, mean and standard deviation values are calculated. The result is discussed below.

Table 3: Employees Perception on Green HR Planning

Green Human Resource Planning	Mean	Std. Dev.
It has planned number of employees capable of carrying out environmental activities.	4.53	0.78
Green management initiatives have enough skills.	4.46	0.93
It has appointed the consultants to forecast the environmental works	4.29	0.99
Applied strategy to preserve environment.	4.20	1.14
Total	4.35	0.85

Green human resource planning is analyzed with four statements in the five point scale. Further, mean and standard deviation are reckoned for each statement. The result is displayed in the table 3. The calculated mean values are ranged from 4.22 to 4.52. The calculated standard deviation values are ranged between 0.78 and 1.14. From the mean values, it is observed that the faculty members have highly perceived that the organism has planned the number of employees capable of carrying out environmental activities (4.53) followed by the green environmental management initiatives have enough skills (4.46), the company appointed the consultants to forecast the environmental works (4.29) and the company has applied strategy to preserve environment (4.28). The total mean score for green human resource planning is 4.35. It is inferred that the organisation has well planned about the environmental management. The colleges have effectively implemented the cleaner production, responsible care to manage their environmental issues. However, the faculty members felt that the colleges have not effectively applied strategy to preserve environmental. Lober (1996) stated that the colleges could conduct more activities relating to waste management, pollution control system and mitigating environmental releases. Arulrajah, Opatha and Nawaratna (2015) stated that the implementation of corporate environmental programme is the good practice to manage environmental issues.

Table 4: Employees Perception about Green Recruitment Practices

Green Recruitment Practices	Mean	Std. Dev.
Communicating the environmental performance through recruitment message.	4.48	0.99
Giving priority to the candidates with green mind set.	4.12	1.23
Using e-technology in the recruitment process	4.20	1.02
Using green employer branding to attend the employees	4.16	1.20
Initiate environmental work force through green recruitment by raising awareness.	4.38	1.08
Total	4.26	1.10

Now-a-days all the organization are more concerned about environment issue. It has own environmental policy and environmentally oriented work force. Searching best green practices is important to the organisation. Table - 4 showed the employees perception towards green recruitment practices. Green recruitment practices are analyzed with 5 statements in the five point scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated for each statement. The calculated mean values are ranged from 4.12 to 4.48. The calculated standard deviation values are ranged between 0.99 and 1.23. From the mean values, it is observed that the faculty members highly rated that during the requirement process, the colleges have communicated the environmental performance through recruitment message (4.48) followed by during the requirement process the organization initiate the environment work force by raising awareness

(4.38), this organization is using e-technology in the recruitment process (4.20), using green employees branding to attract the employees (4.16) and giving priority to the candidates with green mind set (4.12). The total mean score for green recruitment practices is found to be 4.26. It shows that the faculty members have agreed that the organization is excellent in green recruitment practices. The colleges have explained to the candidates with regards to the environmental performance. But, it is found that the colleges are not giving much priority to the candidate with green mind set. Sudin (2011) stated that the employees are required to possess sufficient amount of knowledge and skills related to greening. Then only, it is possible to become green employees. Recruiting potential and hiring quality staffs are very crucial challenges in the war of talent (Renwick, et. al., 2013).

Table 5: Employees Perception about Green Job Designation

Job Designation	Mean	Std. Dev.
Environmental dimension is included in the job description.	4.36	1.12
Green competency is required as a special component in the job specifications.	4.37	1.02
Encouraging team work to preserve the environment.	4.39	0.96
Environmental management function has been developed within the organization.	4.28	1.05
Total	4.31	0.93

Job description can be used to specify a number of environmental task, duties and responsibilities. Job design is analyzed with four statements in the five point scale. Further, mean and standard deviation are calculated for each statement. The result is displayed in the table 5. The calculated mean values are ranged from 4.26 to 4.37. The calculated standard deviation values are ranged between 0.96 and 1.12. From the mean values, it is noted that the employees have highly rated that the team work is encouraged to preserve the environment in the colleges (4.39) followed by green competency is required as a special component in the job specifications (4.37), environmental dimensions are included in the job description (4.36) and environmental management function has been developed in the colleges (14.28). The total mean score of job design is 4.35, it is inferred that the faculty members have stated that the colleges are effectively implementing the green job design in the job description. However, the colleges have not given much importance towards environmental management function in job description. Jabbour, et. al., (2010) stated that some companies use team work and cross functional team as job design technique to successfully manage the environmental issues of the organisation.

Table 6: Employees Perception about Green Selection Practices

Sl. No.	Green Selection	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	Candidates selection based on awareness who have environmental concern of greening job.	4.40	0.96
2.	Preferring candidates who are conscious about green policies.	4.26	1.07
3.	Selection team asking question relating to green practices.	4.31	1.09
4.	Selection criteria with environmental awareness for selecting candidates.	4.02	1.31
	Total	4.24	1.01

During the selection process, the companies considered the candidates environmental concern and interest. Environmentally friendly people can select in addition to the normal selection criteria. Table – 6 explains the employees perception about green selection. Green selection is analyzed with four statements in the five point scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated. The calculated mean values are ranged from 4.40 to 4.02. The calculated standard deviation values are ranged between 0.96 and 1.31. From the mean values, it is observed that these colleges considered the candidates who have environmental concern of green in job selection (4.40), followed by, during the interview, the employer asked the question relating to green HRM practices (4.31), applicants are selected, who are conscious about green policies (4.26) and the selection criteria with environmental awareness for selecting candidates (4.02). The faculty members have perceived that the colleges have the excellent in green selection practices. But, the colleges have not taken much serious about the selection criteria with environmental awareness. Revil (2000) stated that any organization can adopt to select environmental friendly people in the job vacancies. During the interview the candidates should be evaluated by asking environmental related questions (Wehrmeyer, 1996).

Table 7: Employees Perception about Green Induction Practices

Sl. No.	Green Induction	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	Conduct orientation programme to the employees for increasing awareness of green culture	4.39	1.05
2.	Providing necessary information on green management for new employees.	4.30	0.99
3.	Ensuring that new employees are aware of the importance of environmental responsibilities.	4.12	1.03
4.	Making the faculty members to engage in green citizenship behavior.	4.20	1.09
	Total	4.25	0.94

Candidates are getting basic information about the corporate environmental management policy, system and practice. Organizations do specific induction to their employees relating to green. Table - 7 shows the employees perception on green induction practices in the colleges. Green induction is analyzed with four statements in the five point scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values are calculated. The calculated mean values are ranged from 4.39 to 4.12. The calculated standard deviation values are ranged between 0.99 and 1.09. From the mean values, it is observed that the faculty members have highly perceived that the colleges were conducting orientation programmes to the employees for increasing awareness of green culture (4.39) followed by providing necessary information on green management for new employees (4.30), ensuring that new employees are aware of the importance of environmental responsibilities (4.20) and making the faculty members to engage in green citizenship behavior (4.12). It is inferred that the faculty members have agreed that the institutions are doing well about the green induction programmes. But, the colleges are not making the new employees familiar with greening efforts and do not encourage the employees to have green interpersonal behavior. Renwick, et. al., (2013) stated that the company induced the employees should become familiar with environmental culture within the organization.

Table 8: Employees Perception towards environmental performance

Environmental Performance	Mean	Std. Dev.
Disposal of waste without affecting environment.	4.40	1.05
Practices of recycling of materials in the colleges.	4.48	0.89
Usage of renewable energy and sustainable fuels is increasing.	4.30	1.07
Frequency of environmental mishaps is reduced.	4.29	1.10
Conserving water usage	4.60	0.75
Energy usage is being conserved.	4.16	1.26
Total	4.37	1.02

Green training and development programmes should emphasis on the social equity, reduction of environmental risk and ecological scarcities. Table-8 portrays the employees perception about environmental performance. Environmental performance is analyzed with six statements in the five point scale. Further, mean and standard deviation are calculated for each statement. The calculated mean values are ranged from 4.60 to 4.16. The calculated standard deviation values are ranged between 0.75 and 1.26. From the mean values, it is inferred that the faculty members have highly rated that the colleges are concentrating in conservation of water usage (4.48), disposal of waste without affecting environment (4.40), usage of renewable energy and sustainable fuels is increasing (4.30), frequency of environmental mishaps is reduced (4.29) and energy usage is being conserved (4.16). The total mean score of green training and development practices is 4.37. It is inferred that the colleges are having the practice of recycling of materials. And it is observed that conservation of energy usage is at low level among the faculty members. Daily, et. al., (2007) found that the formation of effective green management system directly depends on environmental training. Renwick, et. al., (2013) stated that training programs include green analysis of work place. There is a need for potential green managers within the organization for job rotation. Environmental management training, recycling, waste management and energy efficiency are frictionally required for the people to be green.

Fig 1: Relationship between GHRP and Environmental Performance

Figure-1 explains the relationship between green HRM practices and environmental performance. Here it is hypothesized that green HRM practices have been related with the environmental performance of the institution. Pearson correlation test is applied to test the hypothesis. From the calculated P-values for all the dimensions are found to be significant with the environmental performance. Hence the hypothesis gets accepted. The r-value interprets that the green HR practices of green HR planning, green recruitment, green selection, green job description and green induction are have positive relationship with the environmental performance in the institution. The green HR planning is found to be at high level in the institution among the faculty members. However the green induction practice is found to be at low level in the institution according to the faculty members.

9. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATION

- ❖ It is found that the institution has well planned about the environmental activities. But the faculty members have opined that the colleges have not effectively applied the strategy to preserve the environment. So the colleges may conduct more activities relating to waste management and preservation of environment.
- ❖ The faculty members have agreed that their colleges are having excellent in green recruitment process but it is found that the colleges are not giving much priority to the candidates with green mindset. So the colleges may give importance in recruiting potential and hiring quality staffs to make the environment green.
- ❖ It is observed that the colleges are effectively implementing the design in the job description. However the are not giving much importance towards environmental management function is the institutions. So team work can be assigned to manage the environmental issues of the organization successfully.
- ❖ It is found that the colleges are involving in green selection of candidates. But, the colleges are not giving much importance to the selection criteria of candidates with environmental awareness. So the institutions may adopt to select environmental friendly people in job vacancy and the candidates may be evaluated by asking environmental related questions.
- ❖ The faculty members have agreed that their colleges are doing will about the green induction programmes but the efforts of making new employees familiar in green interpersonal behavior are found to be less. So the colleges may induce their faculty members to become aware of the environmental culture within the institutions.
- ❖ It is found that the colleges are having the good practice of respecting of materials but the conservation of energy usage is found to be at low level in the institution. So the colleges may give environmental training programmes in waste management and energy efficiency to make their environmental green.
- ❖ It is found that the green HR planning in the colleges are found to be good but the green induction practice is found to be at low level. So the colleges may involve in conducting orientation programme to the new employees for increasing awareness of green culture.

10. CONCLUSION

This paper aims to analyse the faculty members understanding of green HRM practices and its effect on environmental performance. The study result revealed that the faculty members understood the importance of green HRM in the present global warming. The study result also indicates that the green HRM helps in environmental sustainability so the institutions may try to implement the green HRM practices in all aspects. Green HRM is a human resource strategy supporting pro-environmental corporate management. Benefits of implementing HRM practices results in ecological awareness of the staffs working, which in turn leads to the sustainability of organizational performance. The findings of this paper have provided some ways to improve the green HRM practices and its implementation may leads to excellent organizational sustainability. GHR practices is a legitimate field of academic pursuit. It has the potential to offer new insights into transformation of the instituting into green environment place.

References

- 1) Beard, C. and Dees S. (2000). Green Teams and the Management of Environmental Change in a UK County Council. *Environmental Management and Health*, 11, 27-38.
- 2) Chaudhary, R. (2019). Green Human Resource Management in Indian Automobile Industry. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 10(2), 161-175.
- 3) Chow, W. and Chen, Y. (2012). Corporate Sustainable Development: Testing a New Scale Based on Mainland Chinese Context. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 105(4), 519–533.
- 4) Cook, Daily, B. F. and Huang, S. (2001). Achieving Sustainability through Attention to Human Resource Factors in Environmental Management. *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 21(12), 1539–1552.
- 5) Cook, J. and Seith, B. J. (1992). Designing an Effective Environmental EMS Training Program. *Journal of Environmental Regulation*, 2(1), 53-62.
- 6) Cook, J. and Seith, B. J. (1992). Designs an effective environmental EMS training program. *Journal of Environmental Regulation*, 2(1), 53-62.
- 7) Crosbie, I, and Knight, K. (1995). Strategy for Sustainability Business : Environmental Opportunity and Strategic Choice. *McGraw-Hill*, Maidenhesd: England.
- 8) D’Mello, S., Wiernik, B. M., Ones. D. S., and Dilchert, S. (2011). The Relationship between Educational Level, Income and Environmentalism: A Meta- Analysis. *Conference for Industrial and organizational Psychology, Chicago, Illinois*.
- 9) Daily, B. and Huang, S. (2001). Achieving Sustainability Through Attention to Human Resource Factors in Environmental Management International. *Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 21(12), 1539-1552.
- 10) Daily, B. F., Bishop, J. and Steiner, R. (2007). The Mediating Role of EMS Teamwork as it Pertains to HR Factors and Perceived Environmental Performance. *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 23(1), 95-109.
- 11) Monicah Wanjiku Kuria (2019). Effect of Green Human Resource Management Practices on Organizational Effectiveness of Universities in Kenya. *Human Resource and Leadership Journal*, 4(2), (1 -20).
- 12) Opatha, Henarath. (2013). Green Human Resource Management: A Simplified Introduction.

- 13) Parul Deshwal, D. (2015). Green HRM: An Organizational Strategy of Greening People. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(13), pp. 176-181.
- 14) Sathya and Jothi Jayakrishnan (2019). Green HRM Business Practices for Implementation in Environmental Performance. *Indo Global Journal of Applied Management Science*, 6(1), 36-40.
- 15) Volkan Ugur (2021). A Story on Sustainability: Both the firm and the Employees are Green Pazarlama. *Teorisi Ve Uygulamalan Dergisi*, 5(1), 161-190.
- 16) Vuyokazi Mtembu (2022). Does having knowledge of Green human resource management practices influence its implementation within organizations? *Problems and Perspective in Management*, 17(02), 267-276.
- 17) Wehrmeyer, W. (1996). *Greening People – Human Resources and Environmental Management*, Sheffield, England: Greenleaf Publishing.